

CYP 2E1 and 1B1 Polymorphisms and their Association with HNSCC: A Meta-Analysis

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Abstract

To investigate the association between CYP2E1 and 1B1 polymorphism and HNSCC risk, we retrieved a total of 37 studies summarizing information, CYP 2E1 (CYP-2E1 -1053C>T, CYP-2E1 -7632T>A) and 1B1 (CYP-1B1 L432V) polymorphisms were included in our meta-analysis. Random or fixed effect methods were used for the analysis. We calculated the odds ratios with their 95% confidence intervals to assess the association between CYP2E1 and 1B1 polymorphism and HNSCC risk. Using random or fixed effect methods, we found statistically significant association of CYP-2E1 -1053C>T, CYP-2E1 -7632T>A and CYP 1B1 polymorphisms with HNSCC risk without any evidence of publication bias or significant heterogeneity. A positive association was also found concerning CYP-2E1 -1053C>T, CYP-2E1 -7632T>A and HNSCC. In subgroup analyses by race, the same significant risks were found among Asian. However, no association was found for CYP-1B1 L432V in the development of HNSCC. Further studies may contribute to the investigation of the potential multigenetic predisposition of HNSCC and reinforce our findings.

Keywords: Head and neck squamous cell carcinoma; CYP 2E1; CYP 1B1; Polymorphism

Abbreviations: HNSCC: Head and Neck Squamous Cell Carcinoma; CYP: Cytochrome P450; CYP2E1: Cytochrome P450 2E1; Ors: Odds ratios; Cis: Confidence intervals; PAH: Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbon

Introduction

Head and neck squamous cell carcinoma (HNSCC) is a low survival and high morbidity cancer when diagnosed in advanced stage, which is a multifactorial disease, including genetic and environmental factors [25]. Tobacco smoking and alcohol abuse have been described as the most important risk factors for developing this carcinoma, but recently many studies show that genetic factors play an important role in determining susceptibility and predisposition to HNSCC by genetic epidemiological survey [6,11,22]. For instance, the activation (phase I) and detoxification (phase II) enzymes are involved in the metabolism of carcinogens, which may interfere with susceptibility to HNSCC [24]. And the activity of phase I enzymes are coded by the cytochrome P450 (CYP) family, which may have implications for the metabolism of chemical compounds in tobacco and alcohol [21].

Cytochrome P450 2E1 (CYP2E1), as a phase I enzyme involving metabolic activation of procarcinogens, located on chromosome 10q26.3 and contains two polymorphisms at nucleotides -7632T>A and -1053C>T upstream which are detectable by Dra I (rs6413432) and PsaI [7,8]. The genetic polymorphism of CYP2E1 has been associated with the risk of cancer, such as lung cancer, hepatocellular carcinoma and pharyngeal [3,14,30]. Studies also have described significant associations between CYP2E1 polymorphism and the incidences of HNSCC [10,13], but those results are inconsistent and inconclusive. Another important phase I enzyme of carcinogen metabolism CYP1B1 gene, located in chromosome 2p22-p21, encodes a 543-amino acid protein. Four sense single nucleotide polymorphisms are found to lead to amino acid substitution of Arg to Ser at position 48 (CYP1B1*2), Ala to Ser at position 119 (CYP1B1*3), Leu to Val at position 432 (CYP1B1*4) and Asn to Ser at position 453 (CYP1B1*5) [1]. Several studies have shown that there is an association between susceptibility to a variety of cancers and polymorphisms of CYP1B1, including breast,

colon, lung, skin and oesophagus [19], especially in the early stages of tumor development [20].

Many studies have investigated the role of CYP2E1 and 1B1 polymorphisms in the development of HNSCC. However, these studies have yielded inconsistent and inconclusive results, which could be due to the small effect of the polymorphism on HNSCC risk and the relatively small sample in each case-control studies. To further evaluate the role of the CYP 2E1 and 1B1 polymorphism in the development and progression of HNSCC, we performed a large case-control study to investigate the association between CYP2E1 and 1B1 polymorphisms and HNSCC risk.

Materials and Methods

Identification and eligibility of relevant studies

The electronic databases, including PubMed, Embase and Web of Science were searched using the key terms: “cytochrome p450 2E1”, “CYP2E1”, “cytochrome p450 1B1”, “CYP1B1”, “polymorphism”, or “oral-cancer” or “larynx” or “pharynx” and “cancer” or “carcinoma”, “HNSCC” or “SCCHN”, or “head and neck cancer” without restriction on language. The data was drawn from all publications up to July 2013. All the searched studies were retrieved, and their references were checked as well for other relevant publications.

Data extraction

Least two investigators independently extracted the data and reached consensus on all items. The following criteria were met in

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eligible studies: (1) they were retrospective or prospective cohort case-control studies with complete genotype distribution data. (2) the diagnosis of HNSCC was confirmed histologically or pathologically. (3) they were original data on genotype frequencies. (4) the distribution of genotypes in both cases and controls should be available. The following data were collected: the first author's surname, publication year, ethnicity, country of origin, numbers of genotyped cases and controls.

Statistical analysis

The association between CYP2E1 and 1B1 polymorphisms and the susceptibility of HNSCC was measured by odds ratios (ORs) with 95% confidence intervals (CIs). Heterogeneity assumption was checked by the chi-square-based Q-test [4]. $P > 0.10$ for the Q-test indicated heterogeneity lack among studies, so the pooled OR was estimated by calculating the fixed-effects using the Mantel-Haenszel method [18]. Otherwise, random-effects models with DerSimonian and Laird method were then used to pool the results [5]. For CYP 2E1, we investigated the associations between genetic variants and cancer

risk in recessive genetic model, dominant genetic model, homozygous wild-type, heterozygous model and allelic contrast. The same method was also applied to analysis of the CYP 1B1. Ethnic group was defined as Asian, Caucasian or Mix. Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium (HWE) was tested by the Chi-square test. If controls of studies were found not to be in HWE, sensitivity analyses was performed with and without these studies to test the robustness of the findings. All of the calculations were performed using the STATA 12.0 (Stata Corporation, College Station, TX). All the P-values were two sided. Publication bias was investigated by funnel plots and Egger's linear regression test [2].

Results

Study characteristics

Twenty-three case-control studies met our inclusion criteria. For the CYP2E1-PstI/RsaI polymorphism, 23 studies were identified and included 6068 cases and 5876 controls; and for the DraI polymorphism 10 studies were identified and covered 2944 cases and 2224 controls.

First author, Country, year	Ethnicity	case/control	HWE(control)
CYP 2E1 -1053C>T			
Hsin-Chia Hung, Taiwan, 1997	Asian	41/122	0.533
Christiane F.S, Brazil, 2005	Mixed	231/212	0.362
S.Liu, New York, 2001	Caucasian	112/224	0.629
S.Liu, New York, 2001	Mixed	145/164	0.968
Shunji Morita, Japan, 1999	Asian	231/212	0.861
Christine Bouchardy, France, 2002	Caucasian	250/172	0.755
Athanasios I. Zavras, Greece, 2002	Caucasian	93/99	0.96
Gattas GJ, Brazil, 2006	Mixed	38/102	0.76
Sugimura T, Japan, 2006	Asian	122/241	0.886
Buch SC, USA, 2008	Caucasian	190/403	0.307
Soya SS, India, 2008	Asian	92/147	0.579
Katoh T, Japan, 1999	Asian	350/350	0.85
Natha 'lia Moreno Cury, Brazil, 2012	Mixed	217/334	0.22
Soya SS, India, 2008	Asian	408/220	0.784
Allan Hildesheim, Taiwan, 1997	Asian	364/320	0.13
Matthias C. German, 1998	Caucasian	379/175	0.697
MV González, Spain, 1997	Caucasian	75/200	0.433
Marzena Gajicka, Poland, 2005	Caucasian	388/323	0.606
Thomas Neuhaus, German, 2004	Caucasian	312/297	<0.05
Narisorn Kongruttanachok, Thailand, 2001	Asian	217/297	<0.05
D Lucas, France, 1996	Caucasian	309/260	<0.05
Jun Tai, China, 2010	Asian	278/278	0.563
Ribeiro Olivieri, Brazil, 2009	Mixed	1226/724	0.314
CYP 2E1 -7632T>A			
Christine Bouchardy, France, 2002	Caucasian	250/172	0.706
Katoh T, Japan, 1999	Asian	92/147	<0.05
Natha 'lia Moreno Cury, Brazil, 2012	Caucasian	174/278	0.09
Soya SS, India, 2008	Asian	408/220	0.439
Allan Hildesheim, Taiwan, 1997	Asian	364/320	0.13
Matthias C. German, 1998	Caucasian	347/121	0.211
Thomas Neuhaus, German, 2004	Caucasian	262/236	0.522
D Lucas, France, 1996	Caucasian	309/258	0.752
Ruwali M, Indian, 2009	Asian	350/350	<0.05
Tomotaka Sugimura, Nagoya, 2006	Asian	241/122	0.910
CYP 1B1*3			
Arvind P. Singh, India, 2007	Asian	150/150	0.466
Guojun Li, America, 2005	Caucasian	100/100	0.856
Yon Ko, German, 2001	Caucasian	312/300	0.418
Jun Tai, China, 2010	Asian	278/278	0.119

Table 1: The baseline characteristics of all eligible studies.

Four studies with 840 cases and 828 controls were retrieved based on the search criteria for HNSCC susceptibility related to the CYP1B1 polymorphisms. The frequency distribution of genotypes in the controls of all the studies was in agreement with HWE except five studies [15-17,23,26]. The detailed characteristics of these studies were summarized in Table 1.

Meta-analysis

CYP 2E1 -1053C>T: The results of our meta-analysis were shown in Table 2. For CYP 2E1 -1053C>T polymorphism, the OR of homozygote c2/c2 and dominant model for total HNSCC were 1.61 (95% CI=1.158-2.225, Pheterogeneity=0.603) and 1.61 (95% CI=1.162-2.216, Pheterogeneity=0.57), respectively. We didn't find any statistical

Sub-grouped studies	Genetic model	Test of association CYP 2E1 -1053C>T		Test of heterogeneity CYP 2E1 -1053C>T		Test of association CYP 2E1 -7632T>A		Test of heterogeneity CYP 2E1 -7632T>A	
		OR (95% CI)	P	P	I ²	OR (95% CI)	P	P	I ²
Over	c1c1 vs c1c2	1.02(0.867-1.199)	0.814	0.069	32.3	1.208(0.982-1.485)	0.073	0.02	54.2
	c1c1 vs c2c2	1.605(1.158-2.225)	0.004	0.603	0.0	1.540(1.049-2.261)	0.028	0.20	42.2
	recessive model	1.055(0.903-1.234)	0.499	0.07	32.2	1.231(1.023-1.482)	0.028	0.05	46.5
	dominant model	1.605(1.162-2.216)	0.004	0.568	0.0	1.351(0.77-2.37)	0.294	0.13	38.2
	allele	1.082(0.915-1.281)	0.356	0.013	44.7	1.228(1.095-1.377)	0.000	0.12	36.3
Asian	c1c1 vs c1c2	1.017(0.867-1.194)	0.833	0.523	0.0	1.218(0.902-1.644)	0.199	0.02	66.3
	c1c1 vs c2c2	1.797(1.232-2.622)	0.002	0.405	2.7	1.643(1.083-2.494)	0.02	0.16	42.2
	recessive model	1.086(0.932-1.267)	0.290	0.608	0.0	1.268(1.009-1.593)	0.042	0.113	46.4
	dominant model	1.781(1.228-2.584)	0.002	0.349	10.5	1.487(0.771-2.866)	0.236	0.08	56.5
	allele	1.142(1.003-1.30)	0.045	0.632	0.0	1.254(1.011-1.555)	0.001	0.44	0.00
Mixed	c1c1 vs c1c2	1.246(0.689-2.255)	0.467	0.002	73.1	0.927(0.564-1.524)	0.766	-	-
	c1c1 vs c2c2	1.662 (0.335-8.259)	0.534	-	-	-	-	-	-
	recessive model	1.253(0.701-2.241)	0.447	0.003	72.4	1.231(1.023-1.482)	0.766	-	-
	dominant model	1.696 (0.341-8.426)	0.518	-	-	-	-	-	-
	allele	1.489(0.710-3.123)	0.292	0.007	71.8	0.934(0.583-1.498)	0.6	-	-
Caucasian	c1c1 vs c1c2	0.919(0.692-1.221)	0.562	0.502	0.0	1.276(0.873-1.866)	0.209	0.09	53.7
	c1c1 vs c2c2	1.035(0.496-2.161)	0.926	0.603	0.0	1.07(0.40-2.864)	0.892	0.252	26.7
	recessive model	0.932(0.712-1.221)	0.609	0.459	0.0	1.252(0.829-1.890)	0.285	0.047	62.2
	dominant model	1.051(0.504-2.193)	0.895	0.599	0.0	0.917(0.259-3.246)	0.893	0.287	20.6
	allele	0.850(0.590-1.224)	0.383	0.091	41.4	1.240(0.984-1.562)	0.068	0.029	66.7

Table 2: Stratified analysis of the CYP2E1 polymorphism and HNSCC.

significance for meta-regression analysis in all three models (for c1/ c2 vs. c1/c1: OR=1.02, 95% CI=0.867-1.199, Pheterogeneity=0.07; for (c1/c2+c2/c2) vs. c1/c1: OR=1.055, 95% CI=0.903-1.234, Pheterogeneity=0.07; for c2 vs. c1: OR=1.082, 95% CI=0.915-1.281, Pheterogeneity=0.01; Figure 1). In the stratified analysis by ethnicity, significant risks were found among Asian for homozygote c2/c2, dominant model and allele c2 (OR=1.797; 95% CI: 1.232-2.622; Pheterogeneity=0.405; for (c1/c2+c1/c1) vs. c2/c2: OR=1.781, 95% CI=1.228-2.584, Pheterogeneity=0.349; for c2 vs. c1: OR=1.142, 95% CI=1.003-1.30, Pheterogeneity=0.632). However, among Mix populations and Caucasians, no significant association was found in all genetic models, suggesting that ethnicity may influence the association results on this SNP and HNSCC risk.

CYP 2E1 -7632T>A: We also analyzed the CYP2E1 DraI

polymorphisms for each ethnic group. All in all, the overall analysis yielded significant estimates (D allele vs. C allele: OR=1.228, 95% CI=1.095-1.377, Pheterogeneity=0.12; DD vs. CC: OR=1.54, 95% CI=1.049-2.261, Pheterogeneity=0.2; DD vs. DC+CC: OR=1.231, 95% CI=1.023-1.482, Pheterogeneity=0.05). In subgroup analysis by ethnicity, significant risks were found among Asian for homozygote CC and allele C (OR=1.643; 95% CI: 1.083-2.494; Pheterogeneity=0.16; OR=1.254, 95% CI=1.011-1.555, Pheterogeneity=0.44; Figure 2). However, no significant association was found in all genetic models of Mixed populations and Caucasians, suggesting that ethnicity may affect the association results on this SNP and HNSCC risk.

CYP 1B1*3: Overall, no statistically significant HNSCC risks were observed for the heterozygous (OR=1.074; 95% CI: 0.814–1.417), the homozygous mutant genotypes (OR=1.139; 95% CI: 0.70–1.855), allele

Figure 2a: OR of HNSCC associated with CYP2E1 DraI for the DD genotype compared with the CC genotype; **b)** OR of oral cancer associated with CYP2E1 DraI for the recessive model.

Sub-grouped studies	Genetic model	Cases/Control	Test of association		Test of heterogeneity	
			OR (95% CI)	P	P	I ²
Over	m1m1 vs m2m2	1464/1954	1.074(0.814-1.417)	0.612	0.056	60.4
	m1m1 vs m1m2	1464/1954	1.139(0.700-1.855)	0.600	0.028	66.9
	recessive model	1464/1954	1.094(0.804-1.489)	0.567	0.015	71.3
	dominant model	1464/1954	1.040(0.861-1.256)	0.683	0.289	20.2
	allele	1464/1954	1.072(0.852-1.349)	0.554	0.015	71.4
Asian	m1m1 vs m2m2	428/428	1.022(0.754-1.384)	0.890	0.670	0.0
	m1m1 vs m1m2	428/428	0.953(0.489-1.857)	0.888	0.592	0.0
	recessive model	428/428	1.011(0.757-1.349)	0.941	0.580	0.0
	dominant model	428/428	0.945(0.489-1.827)	0.867	0.631	0.0
	allele	428/428	1.00(0.781 -1.280)	1.000	0.517	0.0
Caucasian	m1m1 vs m2m2	1036/1526	1.14(0.642-2.024)	0.655	0.007	86.4
	m1m1 vs m1m2	1036/1526	1.252(0.578-2.714)	0.569	0.003	88.5
	recessive model	1036/1526	1.178(0.625-2.221)	0.613	0.001	90.1
	dominant model	1036/1526	1.049(0.861-1.256)	0.633	0.064	70.9
	allele	1036/1526	1.125(0.744-1.700)	0.577	0.002	90.0

Table 3: Stratified analysis of the CYP1B1 polymorphism and HNSCC.

model (OR=1.072; 95%: 0.852-1.349), recessive model (OR=1.094; 95%CI: 0.804-1.489) and dominant model (OR=1.040; 95%CI:0.861-1.256) when compared to the controls (Table 3). But we didn't further evaluate the role of the CYP 1B1*3 polymorphism in the development HNSCC of different ethnicity, because there was not combining a large case-control study.

Publication bias: Begger's funnel plot and Egger's test were used to assess publication bias. The shape of the funnel plots was symmetrical. The Egger test provided evidence that there was no publication bias among the studies included ($p > 0.05$, for all; Figures 3 and 4).

Discussion

Cytochrome P450 (CYP), as mixed function oxidases, is responsible for the human metabolism of drugs, endogenous compounds, environmental and dietary substances. CYP 2E1 is a major component of CYPs, which leads to DNA damage, intensifies lipid and protein peroxidation, and ultimately carcinogenesis [11]. Hildesheim et al. [9] found c2 allele of CYP2E1 gene was 2.6 fold increased the risk of nasopharyngeal carcinoma [9]. Sugimura et al. [28] found carriers homozygous for c2/c2 genotype was 3.38 fold increased the risk of HNSCC compared with the c1/c1 genotype. In addition, CYP1B1, a

Figure 3a: Begg's funnel plot of CYP2E1 Rsa I/Pst I polymorphism and HNSCC risk c2/c2 vs. c1/c1; **b)** Begg's funnel plot of CYP2E1 Rsa I/Pst I polymorphism and HNSCC risk in dominant model.

Figure 4a: Begg's funnel plot of CYP2E1 DraI polymorphism and HNSCC risk DD vs. CC; **b)** Begg's funnel plot of CYP2E1 DraI polymorphism and HNSCC risk in dominant model.

polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon (PAH) metabolizing CYP, has been implicated in the individual susceptibility to chemical-induced cancer. Their et al. [29] suggested that the CYP1B1 codon 432 polymorphism (CYP1B1*3) was a susceptibility factor in smoking-related HNSCC. However, Singh et al. [27] reported that polymorphisms in CYP1B1 were associated with an increased susceptibility to HNSCC, but no significant differences were observed for the distribution of variant genotypes-Leu432Val (CYP1B1*3) [27]. In terms of the CYP2E1 and CYP1B1 polymorphisms and the risk for developing HNSCC, the conclusions of previous studies are not consentaneous.

In this meta-analysis, we examined the association between CYP2E1 and 1B1 polymorphisms and HNSCC risk. Our studies suggested that the variant homozygote and dominant model of the CYP2E1 PstI/RsaI polymorphism were significantly associated with HNSCC risk, when compared to controls. We also observed a significant association between the CYP2E1 DraI polymorphism and HNSCC risk for homozygote, recessive models and allele models in the overall comparisons. Additionally, we analyzed the role of CYP 1B1 polymorphisms in the development of HNSCC. Our results indicated that there was no association between CYP 1B1 polymorphisms and HNSCC risk for all genetic models. Samples about CYP 1B1 polymorphism in HNSCC were not very large, and limited the subgroup analyse with race. However, in subgroup analyse with ethnicity of CYP 2E1, we found a significant conclusion in Asians for CYP 2E1 PstI/RsaI and DraI polymorphism, but not in Mixed populations and Caucasians. Taken together, our findings indicate that the polymorphisms of c2 allele of CYP 2E1 PstI/RsaI and C allele of CYP 2E1 DraI would promote the HNSCC risk and the effect of c2 allele on the risk of HNSCC may differ by ethnicity.

However, some limitations of this meta-analysis should be considered. Firstly, the data of present meta-analysis was a case-control study; the cases were recruited from the hospital and the controls were recruited from the community, selection bias and systematic error may have occurred. Second, HNSCC is a complex disease, but we could not obtain more original data about the age, tobacco, alcoholic and other environment factors. Third, the sample size was relatively small, specifically, about the CYP 1B1 original data.

To conclude, our meta-analysis systematically analyzes the association of CYP2E1 polymorphisms and HNSCC risk. CYP2E1 polymorphisms may be a risk factor for HNSCC, and particularly for Asian populations. But the lack of significant association between CYP 1B1 polymorphism and HNSCC risk. Taken together, much larger sample size and well-matched controls will be required for further association studies. Moreover, gene-gene and gene-environment interactions are necessary to verify these findings.

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